

AN EVALUATION OF THE NEGATIVE EFFECT OF SOME YORUBA CHRISTIAN FILMS ON AFRICAN TRADITIONAL RELIGIOUS ADHERENTS

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Abstract

The colonial masters encouraged the projection of the films that mainly promote their interest and in addition gave support to the Christian Missionaries who also used it as a means to evangelize. Films that tell the story of the life, death, and resurrection of Jesus were projected. In addition to that, they also projected films with a storyline that portrays submission to the Lordship of Jesus as an act of obedience that can fetch salvation, while rebellion against it is disobedience which can lead to eternal damnation. Such were the kind of films projected in Yorubaland to convince and persuade them to accept Christianity. The above assertion is the genesis of media evangelism. This article employs the historical, qualitative, content analysis approach to analyze the films and descriptive methods of research. Generally, in Nigeria today and Yorubaland in particular, the media has become the property of the Christians where they expended essential sum of money to air their programmes on daily basis and for almost twenty-four hours on Sundays. However, findings reveals that conflicts and demonstrations occurred over the production of some evangelical films, like *agbara nla* and *alfa sule* painting the Indigenous religion black which directly or indirectly insult the principle and practices of African Traditional Religion. The article recommends unity, tolerance understanding among others to be the focus of all religious evangelizations. This is

what will bring love, peace, progress and development to the society. This is the interest of this work to fill the gap that can lead to conflict among Yoruba religious adherents.

Key Words: Evangelism, Film, Traditional Religion, Yorubaland, Government.

Introduction

According to Adelola, (2001), films production can be traced to the influence created by the first moving flick in Nigeria otherwise known as the motion picture or celluloid stock through the Balboa and Company, a Spanish firm in 1903. The city of Lagos stands as the base where this moving flick spread to other parts of western Nigeria. It spread slowly to Ibadan in 1921 and to Ijebu Ode in 1929. At this period, Nigerians were under the colonial masters, who exploited the introduction of films in Nigeria by establishing the Colonial Film Unit (CFU). This unit was used as a means for consolidating their power, spreading and imposing their culture on the masses.

In the same vein, the missionaries who had been facing some challenges in their bid to evangelize, gladly embraced this means of spreading the gospel, thereby working hand-in-hand with the colonial masters. These films were projected through the mobile film units in form of a van, with a 16mm projector, a reel of 16mm film and motion picture screen. The films were displayed in the big halls and film theatres. The contents of these films could be rightly imagined, as opined by a popular adage that he who pays the piper dictates the tune. The colonial masters encouraged films that served their interest in enforcing their power and influence under the umbrella of civilization. The church on the other hand manipulated the film industry to enforce Christianity on the people, neglecting their indigenous religions.

The travelling theatre groups were nurtured by Hubert Ogunde, Duro Ladipo, Ade Afolayan a.k.a. Adelove, Moses Olaiya a.k.a. Baba Sala and others (Adu, 2009). The stage plays and cinema productions metamorphosed into the bulk of Yoruba films at the later period. Adedeji and Ekwuazi (1998) commented that the Yoruba theatre has made an indelible impression on the whole of the country. As a travelling theatre, it has taken the theatre to the people and entertained a vast and diverse audience throughout the country. Not earning any subsidies from the government or financial support from any foundation, the artists have progressively managed to survive in a very big way. They draw their income not only from their stage shows but also from television shows, from waxing their music and plays on discs, by printing their plays as photoplays and as literature.

Opubor, Nwuneli and Oreh (1979) in their comment on the first celluloid films produced to aid indigenous languages, which are *Ajani Ogun* (1976) and *Sheu Umar* (1977), observed that the local audience were attracted and at the same time fascinated by the use of their mother tongue language to display a film. Moreover, the Nigerian film industry adopted the name “Nollywood” in 2002. This is an attempt to link the industry to Hollywood in the United States, in the same way that the Indian film industry has its name bearing Bollywood⁴. Many observers and scholars have criticized this, owing to the fact that it does not have any socio-cultural connection with the indigenous film tradition in Nigeria. Haynes (1994) argued that, since popular film in Nigeria developed without external influence in terms of finance and distribution, it should not be tethered to the apron string of Hollywood.

The influx of Yoruba films on video cassette encouraged some religious groups to manipulate the means to propagate their faith. Some of them turned it to tools of war meant to wield at will. With the introduction of films on video cassette and disc, Christian evangelism took a different dimension, which was never condemned until they started using it to malign the image of Yoruba religious adherents. It has been observed that conflicts and demonstrations occurred over the production of some evangelical films, which directly or indirectly insult the Yoruba Indigenous religious adherents. Some of these films include *Agbara Nla*, and the film of dance drama titled “*Sora*” (Take Heed, by a.k.a. AlfaSule). Some of these productions are meant to evangelize Christian’s ideology to the detriment of Yoruba religious adherent’s values.

Examining the stock characters and the Yoruba folkloric video film became the major concern of Ojelabi (2023) as he defines folkloric as a body of traditional beliefs, customs, and expressions, handed down by word of mouth to which every group is bound by common interest and purposes. Folklore according to him in Yoruba film plays a vital role as the source of raw materials particularly for the scripts that leads to productions. This has made some figures prominent and repeated over and over again. He also identified stock folkloric characters as those characters with their root embedded in the folklore of the people. Hence, it is common to find a selected range of familiar mannerism and characterization in the master scene script of the Yoruba film which invariably makes the stories and characters fall under the category of stock types. He concluded that stock characters have set for themselves trademarks, which reflect in their names and costumes. This has made them strong and potent that they seem to sometimes dominate the mind of the producers and directors who appear to have their characters in mind when conceiving the idea for the film. The work extensively dealt with stock folkloric characters in Yoruba films. Since, it did not include religious evangelism through film production; it makes this study valid for research.

Adelola (2001) observed that in African societies, religion and culture are part and parcel of their life and heritage. Thus, the religious aspects of their life cannot be separated, for they are interwoven. She concluded that Nigerian films have been used as instruments of evangelism and as corrective means to solve societal problems. The work dealt with culture and religious values as depicted in some selected films, although, she mentioned evangelism as an instrument through the films to propagate religion, the work does not deeply explore the concept of evangelism. Moreover, the work analyzed some selected films which cut across religion and culture. One of such films is “the gods are dead” which has a direct link to Christian’s evangelism against cultural values, but not interfering with Yoruba religious adherent’s values. It thus, shows the validity of this study on the religious evangelism through films and its effects on the Yoruba cultural principles and practices in Yorubaland.

David defines divination as the practice of attempting to foretell the future, reveal the unknown or find out the wish of a divinity or spirit. He affirmed that Yoruba people regard *Ifa* as a great authority on their mythology, history and philosophy. This gave the reason why *Ifa* oracle is consulted before anything at all is done by them. The types of divination systems in Yorubaland were given and analysed by the author, these includes; *Ikin*, *Opele*, *Eṣerindilogun*, Sandcutting, Watergazing and the use of Kolanut. He focused on divination systems in Yorubaland but not in relation to evangelism in Yorubaland.

Religions in Yorubaland

Defining religion has proved to be difficult from time immemorial. A number of scholars from areas of philosophy, psychology, sociology, anthropology, religion and history have provided definitions that suited their areas of specialization. An attempt to define religion by some of these scholars failed owing to the fact that few aspects of religion were sparsely covered. It should be noted that, religion can be seen as a theological, philosophical, anthropological, sociological, and psychological phenomenon of human kind. Thus, to limit religion to only one of these categories is to miss its multi-facet nature and lose out on complete definition. In other words, the chosen definition must cover all aspects of human life such as beliefs, feelings, experiences, actions, practices, behaviours, thoughts, ethics, education, training, development, success, failure, happiness, material needs, spiritual needs, talking, dressing, eating, drinking, sleeping and worship.

With the above assertion, the definition of Paul Connelly (1996) is considered where he sees religion’s origination as an attempt to represent and order beliefs, feelings, imaginings and actions that arise in response to direct experience of the sacred and the spiritual. He further explained that, as this attempt expands in its formulation and elaboration, it becomes a process that creates meaning for itself on

a sustaining basis, in terms of both its originating experiences and its own continuing responses. Connelly described the sacred as a mysterious manifestation of power and presence that is experienced as both primordial and transformative, inspiring awe and rapt attention. He elaborated further by saying that this is usually an event that represents a break or discontinuity from the ordinary, forcing a re-establishment or recalibration of perspective on the part of the person involved, but it may also be something seemingly ordinary, repeated exposure to which gradually produces a perception of mysteriously cumulative significance out of proportion to the significance originally invested in it.

He also shed light on the aspect of spiritual by seeing it as a perception of the commonality of the mindfulness in the world that shifts the boundaries between self and other, producing a sense of the union of purposes of self and other in confronting the existential questions of life, and providing a mediation of the challenge – response interaction between self and other, one and many, that underlies existential questions. From the analysis of Connelly, it can thus, be deduced that, in some ways the sacred and the spiritual seem to pull in opposite directions, the former toward demarcations and exceptions of startling proportions, the latter toward commonality and blurring of previously accepted boundaries. That most religions include both in their germinal development shows that the differences may be complementary. It is on this note, that, this study examines the component elements of the African Indigenous Religion (AIR).

African Indigenous Religion (AIR)

African indigenous religion identifies itself with various cultures and customs of Africans. The ability to promote unified beliefs put the Yoruba people under the umbrella of African indigenous religion, whose faith is simply referred to as indigenous beliefs in Nigeria. Indigenous belief as used in Nigeria cuts across different ethnic groups who adopted the beliefs and customs of their ancestors. In the making of African indigenous religion, five component elements were identified by Bolaji Idowu (1991), they are; belief in God, belief in divinities, belief in spirits, belief in the ancestors, and the practice of magic and medicine.

African Indigenous Religion and its Spread in Yorubaland

The traditionalists believe in God Who is the Supreme Being and referred to as *Olodumare* as earlier stated, and at other times He is called *Olorun* (the Owner of heaven). His ministers who represented His authority on earth are referred to as *Orisa* (divinities or deities). There is no specified way of direct worship of *Olodumare*, what is known is the worship directed towards His ministers who they believed would grant their biddings. Awolalu (1981) gave four distinct elements of worship which are; liturgy, sacrifice, cultic functionaries and sacred places

Sacrifice

Worship in the indigenous religion is not complete without the element of sacrifice. In the indigenous setting, the whole life of the people depends on the utterance of *Ifa* (the oracle). Whatever that would be done by anyone in the community must first be sought at the feet of *Ifa*. The consultation of *Ifa*, otherwise known as divination always end with prescription of a sacrifice. This is why the Yoruba will say *A ki n difa ka ma yan ebọ* (one does not consult the oracle without prescription of sacrifice). Sacrifice is prescribed for pleasant and unpleasant situations. The offerings of sacrifice may be given daily, weekly or as the occasion demands. Six types of sacrifices were identified by Awolalu (1981), they are; *Ebọ Opẹ ati idapo* (thanksgiving and communion sacrifice), *Ebọ Eje* (votive sacrifice), *Ebọ Etutu* (propitiatory sacrifice), *Ebọ Oju koribi* (preventive sacrifice), *Ebọ Ayepinun* (substitutionary sacrifice) and *Ebọ Ipilẹ* (foundation sacrifice)

Cultic Functionaries

In the indigenous worship, the cultic functionaries who include the officials and the attendants play a significant role in the actualisation of the proper process needed to complement the worship procedures. For each divinity, there is a priest attached to shrine. It is important to note that there are other sacred people who play conspicuous and leading roles during worship. They are *Olori Ebi* (family head), *Oba*, *Baale*, *Oloja* (town or village head), *aworo* (priests), *Elegun* (the medium) and *Oloogun* (the medicine-man). As the divinities stand as intermediaries between man and God, so also does each priest stand as intermediary between man and the deities. They are particularly prominent during great festivals such as the annual sacrificial feast when devotees come together to worship at the shrine. Apart from being the guardian of the shrine, the official ascribed to each divinity has a comprehensive knowledge about such divinity and is in charge to direct worshippers on how to make an appropriate and correct approach to the divine being.

Sacred Places

Ojubọ (the place of worship) is sacred in the belief of the Yoruba. These places of worship are numerous considering the numbers of divinities worshipped in Yorubaland. The names of each worship centre would be according to the divinities worshipped in such shrine. Sometimes, the worship centre may be situated in the grove; such would be referred to as *igbo*. These shrines are sometimes accommodated in one of the rooms in a house, in a screened-off portion of the sitting room, or in a corridor

From the analysis above, it shows how the Yoruba traditionalists have engaged themselves in the worship of the numerous deities in their domains. The spread of

their belief was mainly through the strong faith they have in the efficacy of their traditional modes of worship. Their feasts were celebrated with all grandeur and pageantry, which made worshippers look forward to the next time such events would come up again. At the advent of other religions, and with much conversion to these religions, some of them still come to propitiate the divinity attached to their family tree.

Outline of *Agbara Nla* (The Ultimate Power)

This film was produced in four parts on video discs. The major characters are Işawuru (*Ifa* priest), *Aro Męta* (three powerful witches), brother Kọla and his wife sister Bọse, brother Kunle (Ọlaboye) and his wife sister Mary (Ọlatomi), Pastor and Paulina (*Ayah Matanga*).

Part one of this film features Işawuru (the *Ifa* priest), who collaborates with the *Aro Męta* (the three powerful witches) and the *Olori Emere* in bringing calamities on the inhabitants of *Abule Muwonleru* and its environs which is a wrong notion about the belief of the Africa. Pandemonium, commotion, contention, uproar and calamities on the inhabitant of any communities is not always as a result of their belief in Yoruba religion or the position of the witches and wizard in the contemporary society. Işawuru's fame of being a powerful priest attracted strangers, which brought Engineer and his wife Aduke to his village to seek for remedy to her long time bareness. Aduke who was directed by her friend to visit the *Ifa* priest, had encounter with sister Mary who carried out house to house evangelism to make her accept Jesus into her life for remedy to her problems.

Being adamant, she still went ahead to visit the *Ifa* priest with her husband. Işawuru succeeded in giving them a child through the help of *Olori Emere*, and the bad comment in the film that the child would only spent six years with them after she would have ruined all their wealth is also a derogatory statement about the Yoruba Religion. Brother Kunle (Ọlaboye) and sister Mary (Ọlatomi), who got married recently received the same message given to brother Kọla, they resolved in their minds to go to the place as soon as they get the direction to the village. These couples met Engineer at the hospital where his wife was undergoing labour. The prayer session held in the hospital facilitated the safe delivery of the child.

Part two features Engineer and his wife where they are explaining how they got the child to the couples who visited them in their home. They gave their life to Jesus after the couples had preached to them. Thereafter, they followed the couples to *Abule Muwonleru* to renounced their oath with Işawuru (the *Ifa* priest) and to make the couples know their way when they are set for the mission of evangelism there. The couples (Ọlaboye and Ọlatomi) relocated to *Abule Muwonleru* for a full time evangelism with the intention of redeeming the inhabitants from the clutches of the witches, wizards and other evil spirits that put them in bondage.

Işawuru was not pleased with their presence. He tried to discourage them from staying in *Muwonleru* but the couples stood their ground that they were sent by God and no one can stop them. He then resolved to afflict them with charms that would destroy them. Işawuru was bent on carrying out his evil deed on them by all means but he did not succeed. In his confusion to avert the nemesis of the evil spirit he has invoked, he mistakenly destroyed the life of his only daughter Awofunto and her husband. At Abuja, Bøş made an intimate friend with Paulina in the company she worked with. Paulina showered her with assorted gifts and money. She was also lured into drinking of alcohol, this worried her husband (Kola) who was helpless. In the guise of showing Bøş her relatives, Paulina took her to a big house where she later referred to as her palace. They have to go through a wardrobe where her real name – *Ayah Matangah* was inscribed on the door leading to her main palace. Inside the palace she tries to initiate Bøş, who pleaded not to be initiated and was given the option to come back since she has been exposed to their secret. A covenant was thus reached between them with a sign placed on her forehead.

Part three features Işawuru who never relent in his effort to destroy the couples, even after bringing calamity upon himself. He gathered enormous evil powers to further his aim but was disappointed at every trial. He thus sought to know from the most powerful witches in *Abule Muwonleru*, the *Aro Meta*, the personality of Jesus, since this is the name claimed by those (the couples, Olaboye and Olatomi) he had quarrel with, which they relied on. Alas he was shown the path to salvation. He therefore submitted soberly and destroyed all that he had gathered in charms, and then he became blind. He sought the help of a small boy who took him to the residence of the couples. Işawuru accepted Jesus into his life through the couples and was baptized by the Pastor from Lagos at the sacred river of *ahoyaya* where he preferred the name Paul and ascribed to himself the title Esupofu.

Brother Kola was relieved of his job at Abuja, he also lost his house to fraudster and the greatest affliction on him was the state of his wife who was in coma after telling him what transpired between her and Paulina. Bøş's state of coma was transmitted to insanity where Paulina's evil spirit resides in her body with the name *AyahMatangah*. Brother Kola was forced to come to Lagos to explain his ordeals to Pastor. Bøş was brought to Pastor's residence for intensive prayers. Brother Kola became blind with the influence of the evil spirit of *AyahMatangah*. This evil spirit claimed to be capable of speaking French, Spanish, English and Arabic.

Işawuru, who is now referred to as Esupofu, became fervent in the spread of the gospel in the once dreaded land of *Muwonleru*. He dissociated himself from the *AroMeta* and renamed *Muwonleru* to become *AbuleOminira*. And the last part – part four features how the *AroMeta*'s efforts to kill Esupofu was thwarted and eventually led to their destruction. Esupofu continued his evangelism and was able to convert an old enemy *AgbeyinErin* to Christianity who was also chosen to be the next king

of *AbuleOminira*. The Pastor in Lagos was charged with the responsibility of inviting Esupofo to deliver Bọse from her trauma, which was successfully done after series of private prayer sessions with Bọse.

In the case of brother Kọla, he was linked to the proverb of Jonah and Paul. He was commanded to go to *Muwọnlẹru* to fulfil the prophecy. Though blind, he resolves to go and evangelise there with his wife. At *Muwọnlẹru*, they stopped on the path way, when he was told that they are in the village. He moved forward with hands raised to seek for forgiveness and pray for strength to carry out the mission, his wife joined him. During this process brother Kọla regained his sight; joy and wonder made Esupofo affirmed that Jesus' power is the ultimate power.

Conclusion

Having gone through the components of the Indigenous religions in Nigeria; the historical antecedent of the establishment of these religions in Nigeria in general, particularly in Yorubaland; the use of films in propagating religious faiths and the random sampling of opinions of the religious faithful through questionnaire, thus, made the work to conclude as follows, that:

- Religious evangelism through Christians' films will significantly lead to distortion and media assault on Yoruba indigenous religious adherent's values.
- Religious evangelism through Christians' films will automatically serve as blackmailing and significantly encourage malign effects on the image of the indigenous religious adherents.
- Religious evangelism through Christians' films will underscore, prove wrong and contradict the principle of religious tolerance as preached in Christianity towards other religious beliefs.
- Religious evangelism through Christians' films will automatically signify self-contradiction against promoting peaceful co-existence among other religious faithful in Yorubaland.
- Religious evangelism through Christians' films will definitely mean a defamation and marginalization of the Yoruba religion adherents within Nigerian Film Industry.

Recommendations

Religion as a social institution in Nigeria is recognized as very fragile and sensitive. Any attempt to obstruct its proper functioning and sensitization can lead to calamities of high potency. But for the purpose of ensuring tranquility, serenity and peaceful co-existence among one another, this study thus, recommend that every religious faith should train, breed and build evangelists that would preach the

ultimate reality and the moral tenet which is the pivot and the centre point making up their religious beliefs.

Secondly, every religious faith should desist from and do away with using their evangelistic tools, especially, through the use of films to distort, malign, attack, defame, assault and belittle other religious beliefs, while, these tools should rather be used to promote, disseminate and propagate the image of their religious faiths to persuade and entice more converts.

Thirdly, Christians, Muslims as well as African traditional religious believers should learn to tolerate and accommodate one another bearing in mind that they were representatives of God who caused all humanity to evolved and emanated from One-Source. Perhaps, differences in the mode of worships and beliefs are just issues of circumstances.

Fourthly, Yoruba religious artistes should encourage themselves to promote the true teachings of Yoruba religion. More so, the basic knowledge as well as little effort needed for the acquisition of the knowledge of understanding Yoruba religious adherent and its teachings should be put on and aspired for by the so-called Yoruba religious artistes, while, Yoruba religious adherent's characters should not be recognized as yardstick to judge or measure Yoruba religion. Through this, the fear of marginalization will be absolutely removed and vanished within the Nigerian Film Industry as every religious group will enjoy equal right and good representation in the film industry.

Fifthly, the governments also have a role to play in the implementation of peaceful co-existence between the various religious groups in Nigeria. Government should ensure strict adherence to the section of Nigerian constitution which guide against defamation and assault of one another so as to facilitate peaceful relations among the representatives of the various religious adherents within Nigerian film industry.

Lastly, unity and brotherhood should be the watchword of all religious activities. As a result, every religious adherent should promote peaceful co-existence and do away with act of discrimination, bitterness and hatred towards one another so as to guide against discord, disunity and chaos within Yoruba land in particular and Nigeria as a whole.

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